

THE ROLE OF PRODUCTIVE ACTIVITIES IN TEACHING AND LEARNING
FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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***Abstract.** This article discusses some of the problems and shortcomings in the educational process. The advantages of using high technology in improving the quality of education and teaching students are highlighted.*

***Keywords.** Quality of education, interactive methods, high technology.*

РОЛЬ ПРОДУКТИВНОЙ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ В ПРЕПОДАВАНИИ И
ИЗУЧЕНИИ ИНОСТРАННЫХ ЯЗЫКОВ

***Аннотация.** В данной статье рассматриваются некоторые проблемы и недостатки образовательного процесса. Выделены преимущества использования высоких технологий в повышении качества образования и обучения студентов.*

***Ключевые слова.** Качество обучения, интерактивные методы, высокие технологии.*

Presentation techniques are the ways used by the teacher to focus learners` attention on the meaning, use and sometimes form of new language, when introducing it to them for the first time. Introductory activities are activities used by a teacher to introduce a lesson or teaching topic. These lesson plans show two common and different ways of presenting new language items. There are several differences in how they present them.

- Language is a clear aim and focus of the lesson.
- The teacher first puts the target language (the language selected for learning) into a situation which shows what it means (a situational presentation). (Step 1)
- The teacher then makes sure that the students remember previously studied language needed to practice the new language by eliciting it, asking students to say the language rather than giving it to them. (Steps 2-3)
- The teacher next models the target language and the students just listen. (Step 4)

- The students then repeat the target language in a choral drill, a very controlled or restricted practice activity, one in which they can use only the new language and without making mistakes.

(Step 5)

- The teacher tells students about the grammatical use of the new language. (Step 6)
- The teacher asks the students concept questions, questions that check their understanding of the use meaning of the new language. (Step 7).
- The students then do a controlled practice activity focusing on form (Step 8)
- Then further practice activities focusing on meaning. (Step 9)

You can see that at the presentation stage of a PPP lesson (Steps 4-7) the teacher firstly sets up a context for presenting the new language that shows its meaning, then models (provides a model for students to copy) the target language for students to repeat before highlighting the form and use of the language through drills and concept questions / concept checking, which give students the opportunity to notice and focus on these. The lesson then moves on to a practice stage.

Task - based Learning (TBL) lesson:

- The aim of the lesson is for students to complete a task.
- The teacher starts by contextualizing the topic (putting it in a situation which shows its meaning). (Step 1)
- The teacher gives the students tasks to do. (Steps 3, 4, 5)
- The teacher and students discuss any new or problematic language they needed for the task. (Step 6).
- Lastly, the students do a task to consolidate the language. (Step 7)

You can see that in a TBL lesson the presentation of new language (Step 6) in fact follows the stage in which students use the new language. This allows the student to focus first on the meaning of the new language rather than its form.

A PPP approach to presenting new language focuses directly on both meaning or use and form of target language and gives students an opportunity to practice language in a safe learning environment where it is difficult to make mistakes. It can therefore be quite a confident-building approach for students. But it makes student learn language items they may not be interested in or ready to learn, and gives them few opportunities to really use the language for communication.

The TBL approach, on the other hand, allows students to find new language when they want to, and to use language experimentally and creatively for real communication. In this way it puts second language learners in a situation which is quite similar to the one in which children

learn their first language. Some learners may find this approach to language learning exciting and challenging. Others may wish for more guidance and structure to help them.

PPP and TBL are not the only ways of presenting new language. It is also possible, for example, to present new language to learners after they have met it in reading or listening text which is first used for comprehension. The teacher could ask students to underline examples of the target language in the text and then work out the meaning or use of that language. This is an example of using guided discovery to present target language. Another possibility is to do an oral activity such as a discussion on a topic or a task such as designing a new playground for the school, then introduce new language while the discussion or task is happening.

Another way of focusing on new language is through Test-teach-test. In this, the teacher first gives learners a task that requires them to use target language. If this activity shows that the students don't know how to use the target language, the teacher will then present the new language, then give the students another task to practice the new language. If the first task shows that the students already know the target language sufficiently well, the teacher will move on to something else.

You can see that all the presentation techniques contextualize target language i.e. they put the language in a context which shows its meaning. The context can be provided by building a situation, using a listening or reading text, doing a task, using realia, mime (using the body and no words to convey meaning). Explanations, visuals or a combination of these. When learners learn target language they need to know what it means. Contextualising aims to help learners to notice and understand meaning. While all the techniques focus on the meaning of the target language they may not all focus so much on its form. For example, PPP and guided discovery focus on form and meaning, whereas task-based presentations focus more on meaning.

Teachers' different beliefs about how language learning takes place, the role of form and meaning in language learning, their preferred approach(es) to language teaching and the age and needs of their students will decide how much they prefer focus on form.

Introductory activities are different from presentation techniques. They are the activities a teacher uses to introduce a lesson or teaching topic, or sometimes to introduce new students to one another. If you look back at the PPP and TBL lessons on pages 90-1 you will see that they, too, include introductory activities. Step 1 in the PPP lesson provides a lead-in to the topic, and steps 2 and 3 are lead-ins for language needed for the lesson's main aim. In the TBL lesson, steps 1 and 2 are lead-ins.

The introductory stage of a lesson helps students to settle into the lesson and focus on its content. There are two kinds of introductory activities: warmers and lead-ins. Warmers are often used to raise students' energy levels or to make them feel comfortable before the main learning of the lesson starts. They are not always connected to the topic of the lesson: for example, they could be a quiz, game or pairwork activity.

Lead-ins introduce the content of the lesson. Their aim is to focus and motivate students and make a link between the topic of the lesson and the students own lives (personalisation), For example, If students are going to read a text about the internet, rather than giving them the text immediately, we could do one or more lead-in activities such as discussing with students how often they use the internet, what they use it for, what their favourite websites are, etc. Or if in another lesson they are going to listen to a conversation about favourite television programmes, the lead-in activities might be making a list of their favourite television programmes and discussing them with a partner. These activities will probably involve pre-teaching (teaching language before students meet it in a text) key vocabulary for the texts and comprehension tasks that follow.

In some classes students don't know one another at the beginning of term, or new students often join the class. In this situation teachers sometimes do another kind of introductory activity called an ice-breaker. The aim of ice-breakers is for students to get to know one another so that they all feel comfortable with each other in the class. Examples of ice-breakers are doing a mingling survey (learners find out information from others by asking questions or using questionnaires) about the class's interests and hobbies. Another is asking students to work in groups to find out what they have in common, e.g. favourite TV programmes, favourite website, favourite colour.

These particular bands cover a wide range of ability. When working with a particular class it may be more useful for the teacher to work with a narrower range. The bands could be used in a formal assessment of speaking or to help a teacher carry out informal assessment. Informal assessment is sometimes used to assess students behavior, attitudes or learner characteristics rather than their language abilities. In this case the assessment criteria might be e.g. motivation, degree of participation in group work, type of learning style, etc.

Key concepts and the language teaching classroom are:

- Assessment can affect what we teach, how we teach and our learners' motivation for learning. It is very important for tests to have a good influence on teaching and learning.
- Some assessment tasks are easy to write, e.g. essay titles, or mark, e.g. categorizing tasks.

But we need to check if they reflect what we have taught. It is not a good idea to use a particular testing task just because it is easy to use or easy to mark. For example, for administrative reasons, it is often difficult to assess learners' speaking, so speaking is often not assessed, and as a result learners may start thinking that speaking isn't important. Speaking skills can sometimes be more easily assessed informally than formally.

- To really reflect the level of learners' learning, the content and tasks included in progress and summative tests should reflect the content and tasks in our teaching, this may mean that our tests include a mixture of objective and subjective tasks.

- Assessment needs to be fair. This means that progress and summative test should only test what has been taught and that they should be reliable and accurate in their marking. Using bands to help us mark subjective tasks helps achieve this.

- Feedback to learners on what they got right or wrong, their strengths and weaknesses, and what they can do to improve, is very important. Through feedback, assessment helps learning.

- Informal assessment is often much more suitable for assessing young learners than formal assessment. This is because young learners' ways of thinking and learning are based on experiencing and communicating, and also because teachers of young learners are often interested in finding out more about their learners' attitudes, motivation and behaviors.

- If in your school, several classes follow the same syllabus or coursebook and do the same subjective / partly subjective test it is useful for the teachers to use the same assessment criteria or bands. It may be useful to agree what mark you would give to some samples of students' writing before marking starts. Even then, there may be disagreements amongst teachers. At this point, it's useful to discuss exactly what the bands mean. This process helps marking become fairer and more reliable.

- Working with assessment criteria and bands helps the teacher grade all students against the same level of achievement. This can help the teacher and the students know more about their real level of ability than if the teacher just ranks the students according to their grades.

In short, the use of the latest technologies and the use of interactive methods are important in improving the quality of education and providing high quality education to students.

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